

The group of the Fermat Numbers

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Abstract: In this work we are discussing the group that we can obtain if we consider the Fermat numbers with a generalized sum.

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In [1] we find that there are two definitions of the Fermat numbers. We have a less common definition giving a Fermat number as $F_n = 2^n + 1$, which is obtained by setting $x=1$ in a Fermat polynomial of x , and the commonly encounter definition $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1$, which is a subset of the previous assembly of numbers. Here we will consider numbers $F_n = 2^n + 1$ and - as we have recently proposed in [2] for q -integers and Mersenne numbers - investigate the set of them to find its generalized sum which defines the operation of the group.

Let us remember that a group is a set A having an operation \bullet which is combining the elements of A . That is, the operation combines any two elements a, b to form another element of the group denoted $a \bullet b$. To qualify (A, \bullet) as a group, the set and operation must satisfy the following requirements. *Closure:* For all a, b in A , the result of the operation $a \bullet b$ is also in A . *Associativity:* For all a, b and c in A , it holds $(a \bullet b) \bullet c = a \bullet (b \bullet c)$. *Identity element:* An element e exists in A , such that for all elements a in A , it is $e \bullet a = a \bullet e = a$. *Inverse element:* For each a in A , there exists an element b in A such that $a \bullet b = b \bullet a = e$, where e is the identity (the notation is inherited from the multiplicative operation). A further requirement, is the *commutativity:* For all a, b in A , $a \bullet b = b \bullet a$. In this case, the group is an Abelian group. For an Abelian group, one may choose to denote the *operation* by $+$, the *identity element* becomes the *neutral element* and the inverse element the *opposite element*. In this case, the group is called an additive group.

The generalized sum for the Fermat numbers $F_n = 2^n + 1$ is:

$$F_m \oplus F_n = 2 - F_m - F_n + F_m F_n = (1 - F_m) + (1 - F_n) + F_m F_n \quad (1)$$

To have (1), let us evaluate:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{m+n} = 2^{m+n} + 1 &= F_m \oplus F_n = 2 - F_m - F_n + F_m F_n = 2 - (2^m + 1) - (2^n + 1) + (2^m + 1)(2^n + 1) \\ 2^{m+n} + 1 &= 2 - 2^m - 2^n - 2 + 2^m 2^n + 2^n + 2^m + 1 \end{aligned}$$

This gives also the *closure* of the group.

We can provide a recurrence relation as: $F_{n+1} = 2^{n+1} + 1 = F_n \oplus F_1$

From (1), we can see that the *neutral element* is not 0. We have to use as a *neutral element* the integer 2, which is $F_0 = 2^0 + 1 = 2$ and then an element of the group. We have:

$$F_n \oplus F_0 = 2 - F_n - F_0 + F_n F_0 = F_n$$

The *opposite element* is defined by $F_n \oplus \text{Opposite}(F_n) = 2$. We have:

$$\text{Opposite}(F_n) = \frac{F_n}{F_n - 1} = 1 + 2^{-n} = F_{-n} \quad (2)$$

Then, to have a group we need to add numbers (2) to the set of the Fermat numbers.

Therefore, we consider 2 as the *neutral element*, and the *opposite element* as given by (2).

Let us consider three Fermat numbers F_n, F_m, F_l ; to have a group we need the *associativity* of the generalized sum, so that $(F_m \oplus F_n) \oplus F_l = F_m \oplus (F_n \oplus F_l)$. Let us call $x = F_n, y = F_m, z = F_l$ and evaluate:

$$\begin{aligned} (x \oplus y) \oplus z &= 2 - (x \oplus y) - z + (x \oplus y)z = 2 - 2 + x + y - xy - z + 2z - xz - yz + xyz \\ (x \oplus y) \oplus z &= x + y + z - xy - xz - yz + xyz \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

And:

$$\begin{aligned} x \oplus (y \oplus z) &= 2 - x - (y \oplus z) + x(y \oplus z) = 2 - x - (2 - y - z + yz) + x(2 - y - z + yz) \\ x \oplus (y \oplus z) &= x + y + z - xy - xz - yz + xyz \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

From (3) and (4), we have the *associativity*. The *commutativity* is evident.

We have already considered the generalized sum (1) in a recent work [3].

In [3], we consider some functions $G(x)$, having inverses so that $G^{-1}(G(x))=x$, which are *generators of group law* [4-6]:

$$\Phi(x, y) = G(G^{-1}(x) + G^{-1}(y))$$

The *group law* is giving the *generalized sum* of the group $x \oplus y = G(G^{-1}(x) + G^{-1}(y))$.

In [3] we considered the following generator and inverse:

$$G(x) = e^{-2x}(e^{2x} + 1) \quad G^{-1}(x) = \ln\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x-1}}\right) \quad (5)$$

and investigate a possible group from them. The *group law* $\Phi(x, y)$ gives the generalized sum:

$$x \oplus y = G(G^{-1}(x) + G^{-1}(y)) = G\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x-1}}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{y-1}}\right)\right) = G\left(\ln\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x-1}\sqrt{y-1}}\right)\right) = G\left(\ln\frac{1}{Z}\right)$$

$$G\left(\ln\frac{1}{Z}\right) = e^{-2\ln Z}(e^{2\ln Z} + 1) = (x-1)(y-1)\left(\frac{1}{(x-1)(y-1)} + 1\right)$$

$$x \oplus y = 2 - x - y + xy = (1-x) + (1-y) + xy \quad (6)$$

And (6) is the generalized sum (1) proposed for the Fermat numbers.

Let us also note that, if we use (5), we need $x > 1$. And this is a condition satisfied by the Fermat numbers and their opposites (2).

References

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